

THE EFFECT OF HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION, ELECTROLYTES, NORMAL AND IMMUNE SERA ON THE CATAPHORETIC VELOCITY OF *LEISHMANIA TROPICA*. PART I.

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The cataphoretic velocities of bacterial suspension in presence of electrolytes and non-electrolytes, normal and immune sera have been investigated.

The electrical charge of *Leishmania tropica* in a solution of sodium chloride of $p_{\text{H}} 7.0$ is negative and the cataphoretic velocity increases as the concentration of sodium chloride decreases. The nature of the electrical charge on *Leishmania tropica* is reversed between $p_{\text{H}} 3.0$ and $p_{\text{H}} 3.4$. Below $p_{\text{H}} 3.0$, they are positively charged and above $p_{\text{H}} 3.4$ they are negatively charged.

Both immune and normal sera, obtained from rabbits, decrease the cataphoretic velocity of *Leishmania tropica*. The effect is, however, much more pronounced with immune serum than with normal serum. The iso-electric point of *Leishmania tropica*, sensitised with immune serum, is in the neighbourhood of $p_{\text{H}} 5.3$.

The cataphoretic velocity of bacterial suspensions in presence of electrolytes, non-electrolytes, normal and immune sera has been extensively investigated and as a result of such investigation much valuable information on the relation of electrokinetic potential to agglutination (Northrop and de Kriuf, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1921, 4, 639, 655), phagocytability (Topley, "Outline of Immunity", 1933, p. 77), toxigenicity, especially of the diphtheria group (Falk *et al.*, *J. Bacteriol.*, 1928, 18, 6; Thompson, *Amer. J. Hyg.*, 1932, 18, 712) and transition from the 'smooth' to 'rough' variety (Mudd and Mudd, *J. Exp. Med.*, 1927, 48, 173) has been obtained. There are, however, very few such measurements in the case of protozoal bodies. An investigation was, therefore, undertaken to ascertain the effect of electrolytes, hydrogen ion concentration and of normal and immune sera on the cataphoretic velocity of *Leishmania tropica* in aqueous suspension. The results so far obtained are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The micro-cataphoretic method was used in these experiments. The cell was a flat rectangular one, of the type used by Freundlich and Abramson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 128, 25) with this slight modification that it was provided with two detachable side-tubes, one on each side. The joints were carefully ground so as to be leak-proof. Each side-tube carried

an electrode vessel and a three-way stop-cock. The cell was cleansed thoroughly before use and then filled with the desired suspension of *Leishmania tropica*, care being taken to remove all air bubbles. The electrode vessels were filled with copper sulphate solution into which dipped copper electrodes. The connection between the cell and the electrode vessels was established through agar bridges. Just before taking the actual reading, the electrodes were connected with the 220 volt lighting circuit. The current flowing through the system was indicated by a sensitive milliammeter included in the circuit. The velocity of the protozoal bodies was measured at two depths $d/6$ and $d/2$ inside the cell, where 'd' stands for the depth of the cell. For the cell used by us d was found to be 0.81 mm. The actual velocity of the protozoal bodies was calculated from the formula.

$$V = \left(\frac{2}{3}V_1 + \frac{1}{3}V_2\right)$$

where V_1 and V_2 are the observed velocities at depths $d/6$ and $d/2$ respectively inside the cell, as already mentioned.

Effect of Sodium Chloride on the Cataphoretic Velocity.

The cataphoretic velocity of *Leishmania tropica* in solutions of different concentrations of sodium chloride having pH 7.0 was measured and the results are recorded in Table I. The velocity is expressed in cm./sec. per volt/cm. The micro-organisms are found to be negatively charged in these solutions. It will also be noticed from the data given in Table I that the cataphoretic velocity of the protozoa increases as the concentration of sodium chloride diminishes.

TABLE I.

Charge of protozoa—negative.

Percentage conc. of NaCl.	*V.	Percentage conc. of NaCl.	*V.
1.0	18.4	0.4	29.4
0.9	18.9	0.3	34.0
0.8	19.3	0.2	40.1
0.7	20.6	0.1	55.2
0.6	22.8	0.05	59.4
0.5	25.6	0.02	59.9

* V. here and in the following tables indicates the cataphoretic velocities in cm. per sec. per volt/cm. multiplied by 10^5 .

Effect of Hydrogen Ion Concentration on the Cataphoretic Velocity.

The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the cataphoretic velocity of *Leishmania tropica*, suspended in aqueous solutions of glucose and sodium chloride, was determined and the results are recorded in Table II. Citrate-phosphate buffers were used for the p_H range 2.2 to 8.0 and above that range borate buffers were used. The + and - signs used before the figures in columns 2 and 3 indicate the nature of the electrical charge carried by the micro-organisms. It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table II that the electrical charge on the surface of the protozoal bodies is reversed between p_H 3.0 and p_H 3.4. At or below p_H 3.0, the electrical charge of the suspension is positive and its magnitude increases as the p_H decreases. Again at or above p_H 3.4, the charge is negative and its magnitude increases as the p_H increases within the range investigated.

TABLE II.

p_H .	Glucose soln. (V).	0.2% NaCl soln. (V).	p_H .	Glucose soln. (V).	0.2% NaCl soln. (V).
2.2	+23.7	+19.6	5.0	-43.4	-35.7
2.5	+20.8	+18.4	6.0	-53.5	-43.1
2.8	+18.0	+15.9	7.0	-61.4	-48.3
3.0	+ 8.9	+ 8.0	8.0	-67.4	-52.1
3.4	-10.1	- 9.0	9.0	-72.1	-55.7
3.6	-16.5	-15.1	9.5	-74.0	-57.6
4.0	-27.4	-23.2			

Effect of Normal and Immune Sera on the Cataphoretic Velocity.

The effect of normal and immune sera of rabbits on the cataphoresis of *Leishmania tropica* suspended in an aqueous solution of .M/200-phosphate-glycerine buffer (p_H 7.4) was determined. The immune serum was prepared by injecting rabbits repeatedly with increasing doses of *Leishmania tropica*. The immune serum thus obtained gave agglutination up to a dilution of 1 in 8000. The results are recorded in Table III. It will be noticed that the immune serum diminishes the cataphoretic velocity and hence the electrokinetic potential to a much greater extent than the normal serum. At a dilution of one in two thousand, the normal serum affects the

cataphoretic velocity very slightly, changing it from 59·9 to 58·8 cm. only; while the immune serum decreases it to a marked extent from 59·9 to 46·2 cm.

TABLE III.

Cataphoretic velocity in the absence of any serum = 59·9 cm.

Serum dilution.	Normal serum. (V).	Immune serum (V).	Serum dilution.	Normal serum (V).	Immune serum. (V).
1/100	34·7	26·3	1/1200	51·2	38·5
1/200	37·5	28·6	1/1600	55·7	43·1
1/400	43·1	31·6	1/2000	58·8	46·2
1/800	48·5	35·0			

Effect of Hydrogen Ion Concentration on the Cataphoretic Velocity of Sensitised Leishmania Tropica.

The effect of varying the concentration of hydrogen ions on the cataphoretic velocity of *Leishmania tropica* treated with 1/1000 immune serum was also determined and the results are recorded in Table IV. Citrate-phosphate buffers were used in this set of experiments. It will be noticed that in the neighbourhood of p_H 5·3, the cataphoretic velocity of the sensitised micro-organisms is zero. Above p_H 5·3, they are negatively charged and below p_H 5·3 they are positively charged. This shows that the sensitised protozoal bodies have got a protein coating on the surface and the iso-electric point of this adsorbed antibody protein is in the neighbourhood of p_H 5·3.

TABLE IV.

p_H .	V.	p_H .	V.
8·0	-43·5	5·0	+18·5
7·0	-37·1	4·6	+23·5
6·0	-25·0	4·0	+28·7
5·6	-14·6	3·0	+34·2

We offer our grateful thanks to Dr. J. C. Ray, Director, Indian Institute for Medical Research for kindly supplying us with the *Leishmania tropica* suspensions.